

Deliverable 6.5
Final Report on Dissemination, Impact, and Exploitation

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List of Acronyms

5G-PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	6G Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
B5G	Beyond 5G
COTS	Commercial-Off-The-Shelf
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CU	Central Unit
D-MIMO	Distributed MIMO
DPD	Digital-Pre-Distortion
DU	Distributed Unit
EDP	Extended Data Processing
ET	Envelope Tracking
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GA	Grant Agreement
GPU	Graphics processing unit
HW	Hardware
ICT	Information and communication technology
IM	Innovation Manager
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
ISG	Industry Specification Group
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NDT	Network Digital Twin
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OSS	Operational Support System
PA	Power Amplifier
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIA	Research & Innovation Action
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface

RRH	Remote Radio Head
RU	Radio Unit
SAM	Serviceable Available Market
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SNPN	Stand-alone Non-Public Network
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SOM	Serviceable Obtainable Market
TAM	Total Addressable Market
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TMV	Test and Measurement and KPI Validation (SNS Working Group)
UC	Use Case
UPF	User Plane Function
VP	Value Proposition
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity

Executive Summary

This deliverable BeGREEN D6.5 is the “Final report on dissemination, impact, and exploitation”, reporting the work of BeGREEN WP6. It consolidates, updates and completes the following reports:

1. BeGREEN D6.2: ‘Interim Report on Exploitation’ of Task 6.4 (T6.4).
2. BeGREEN D6.3: ‘Interim Report on Dissemination and Communication’ of T6.1.

It includes details about the innovation management methodology applied within BeGREEN and draws some initial conclusions and results obtained until the project end (June 2025). This report evolves the exploitation plan of deliverable D6.1 “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Results” [1].

This document also provides an updated exploitation plan for individual Parties, and an updated market sizing. Particularly, it identifies and summarises the exploitable outcomes from the project. The methodologies for analysing these exploitable outcomes are as well described.

1 Introduction

BeGREEN deliverable D6.5 wraps up the work carried out in the context of BeGREEN WP6 and documents the results of the activities undertaken during BeGREEN's last months. It reports the work carried out across the four WP6 tasks and provides an insight on the impact of the project in terms of dissemination, standardisation, liaison and exploitation activities.

BeGREEN WP6 includes different aspects of identifying and promoting the impact of the BeGREEN project. Accordingly, what unites the four task elements is brought here from a project impact viewpoint. These four elements are:

1. **Dissemination and communication** activities, whose impact is reported and evaluated in the scientific community and beyond. These activities have been reported partially in deliverable D6.3 [2].
2. **Liaisons and interactions with 6G-IA and with external fora**, which have been reported partially in deliverable D6.3 [2].
3. **Exploitation strategies and business modelling**, on one hand promoting activities aimed at exploiting the project results in technological, commercial, and scientific ways, thus enlarging the direct impact of the project in these three realms. In this context this deliverable expands on the initial report on exploitation, i.e. BeGREEN deliverable D6.2 [3], presenting the main exploitable assets created through BeGREEN as well as the exploitation activities and outcomes by project partners. On the other hand, **Business plans and business modelling** work initially devised in deliverable D6.2 is here properly wrapped up around these activities, to ensure a high impact during and beyond the action.
4. **Standardisation activities**, who were initially reported in BeGREEN deliverable D6.4 [4], and are here extended with the latest contributions to Standards Development Organisations (SDOs).

1.1 Document structure

This document comprises 10 chapters. Following the Executive Summary, the following chapters are:

- Chapter 1 introduces the document and provides the context of the dissemination and innovation objectives defined in the BeGREEN Grant Agreement (GA).
- Chapter 2 elaborates the project's dissemination and communication activities of T6.1.
- Chapter 3 describes Liaisons and interactions with 6G-IA and with external fora of T6.3.
- Chapter 4 presents the exploitation strategy, methodology applied by each partner, and the value proposition and the Lean Canvases used by each partner.
- Chapters 5 summarise the main exploitable outcomes identified in BeGREEN and introduces updated individual plans and joint exploitation plans.
- Chapter 6 presents an updated market analysis of the commercialization of the BeGREEN innovation results.
- Chapter 7 assesses the BeGREEN KPI/KVI topic.
- Chapter 8 describes the BeGREEN standards contributions.
- Chapter 9 is the conclusion and summary.

The exploitation goals of BeGREEN are consistent with the scope of the project SNS Stream A call [SNS-2022-STREAM-A-01-01](#), of type RIA action, with results typically of TRL 3-4 (with some limited results of TRL 5) maturity, with significant additional innovation and commercialization efforts required, beyond the results of this project, for true commercial exploitation.

2 Dissemination and Communication Actions

BeGREEN has defined a plan of activities to be performed as described in BeGREEN D6.1 [1]. Table 2-1 presents the list of target Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that BeGREEN has established for the different identified actions. The achievements in dissemination and communication are periodically gathered and compared to the targets. The status is discussed among the partners in WP6-specific calls to drive future actions.

Table 2-1 BeGREEN Targets on Dissemination and Communication

Type of Action	Target KPI	Audience
Website and social media	At least 2 newsletters per year, targeting at least 200 followers on Twitter and LinkedIn, 3000 access to website, 10 videos posted on YouTube channel	Wide public
Scientific publications	At least 15	Research community
Organisation of highly directed workshops	At least 2 workshops as organisers (1 as lead) At least 3 workshops as participants	Research community, Communications industry, Vertical users
Participation in 5G/B5G initiatives	At least 5 participations	Communications industry
Industry exhibitions	At least participation in 10 industrial events with project visibility	Communications industry, Vertical users
Dissemination through training and personal mobility	At least 3 actions	Research community
Datasets published	At least 2	Research community

2.1 Website and social media

Note: The dissemination statistics (website hits, etc) in this document are for the period reported in D6.3 (to February 2024). Updated statistics until the end of the BeGREEN project (end of June 2025) will be provided in the project final review.

2.1.1 Project website

BeGREEN hosts a comprehensive, regularly updated, public website. It contains all relevant project information such as the global vision and objectives, its relation to 6G IA, SNS JU and other projects in the same domain, and the BeGREEN consortium. The site provides access to the public deliverables of BeGREEN, as well as standardisation results, publications, and public materials, such as flyers, posters, and other collateral. The site news channel provides an overview of BeGREEN events and other relevant events. A database, under General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines, has been built and a newsletter will be sent every four six months on average. The official webpage address is (www.sns-begreen.com).

To measure the impact of BeGREEN project website, performance statistics are collected, such as: number of users visiting the website, number of sessions, average session duration, bounce rate, etc. Project management keeps track of social media posts and statistics. Figure 2-1 shows the history of BeGREEN website hits, on months based, twelve months to February 2024 (as reported in D6.3). Furthermore, Figure 2-2 shows the number of hits in the first half of month February 2024, and Figure 2-3 indicates the busiest

day for the website in terms of visits.

Figure 2-1 BeGREEN website hits: 12 months period

Figure 2-2 BeGREEN website hits during the first 15 days of February 2014

Figure 2-3 BeGREEN website busiest day so far (in terms of visits): 152 hits on September 15, 2023

2.1.2X (Twitter)

Figure 2-4 shows BeGREEN X accounts analytics for the period to February 2024 of the project.

Figure 2-4 BeGREEN X account analytics

2.1.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn has established itself as a business and employment-oriented social network. Since LinkedIn is tailored for professionals, it is well suited to communicate the activities and contributions carried out in BeGREEN project. To that end, BeGREEN project management has created a project specific page (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/sns-begreen-project-613259250/>) whose main purpose is to open BeGREEN target audience. The LinkedIn page intends to foster discussions on relevant aspects of the project, advertise news and events, and collect stakeholder’ opinions.

Figure 2-5 shows BeGREEN LinkedIn accounts analytics.

Figure 2-5 Latest analytics and stats of BeGREEN LinkedIn page

2.1.4 YouTube

YouTube is the most popular video-sharing platform in the world. Thus, it is the perfect social channel to broadcast the main activities carried out in the project. For that reason, BeGREEN hosts a YouTube channel that provides video content produced by the project to stakeholders at this address (<https://www.youtube.com/@snsbegreen>). Figure 2-6 shows BeGREEN's YouTube channel.

Figure 2-6 BeGREEN YouTube channel

Many videos were created for MWC2025 and the BeGREEN final event, as well as the final webinar shown below in **Figure 2-7 BeGREEN Final Webinar (30/6/2025)**

Figure 2-7 BeGREEN Final Webinar (30/6/2025)

2.1.5 Partners social channels

In addition to the project specific social media channel, BeGREEN consortium partners are encouraged to post related news and breakthroughs of the project regularly. Figure 2-8 shows some examples.

Figure 2-8 Examples of dissemination of BeGREEN news via partners (Accelleran, i2CAT) social media channels

2.1.6 Newsletters

BeGREEN Newsletter #2 was released on 20th December 2024 with highlights of some project's results, such as:

- Updated BeGREEN Architecture details.
- Summary of the next release of the BeGREEN building blocks [5].
- BeGREEN Intelligence Plane and AI/ML solutions [6].
- BeGREEN presence at EuCNC 2024 and details about the BeGREEN Exhibitor.
- Other related activities.

The newsletter can be accessed on the project website¹.

2.2 White Papers

2.2.1 BeGREEN's "AI-Driven Energy Efficiency for O-RAN" White Paper

BeGREEN White Paper on "AI-Driven Energy Efficiency for O-RAN"² was released in 2025 (see screenshots in Figure 2-9). It is the outcome of an outstanding teamwork by project team, our experts from i2CAT Research Centre, Accelleran and Ericsson, jointly with VIAVI Solutions.

The paper presents the result of BeGREEN Intelligence Plane Implementation and Evaluation by Simulating Realistic O-RAN Environments using VIAVI TeraVM AI RSG. These implementations demonstrated the effectiveness of the BeGREEN Intelligence Plane in achieving significant energy savings, which were

¹ <https://s3.eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/cdn.webfactore.co.uk/10788-begreen%20newsletter%202.pdf>

² <https://s3.eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/cdn.webfactore.co.uk/10788-begreen%20-%20white%20paper%20-%202008.pdf>

visualized through Grafana dashboards tracking metrics, policies, and real-time outcomes.

The BeGREEN Intelligence Plane is set to continue evolving, with future developments aimed at expanding its capabilities and real-world applicability. The project is planning to use more sophisticated AI models to address more complex traffic scenarios, leveraging VIAVI TeraVM AI RSG to generate realistic data for even more accurate simulations.

Figure 2-9 BeGREEN’s “AI-Driven Energy Efficiency for O-RAN” White Paper

2.2.2 BeGREEN contributed to SNS White Paper on KVIs

The recently released white paper on ‘6G KPIs - Definition and Target Values’, is produced by the SNS Test and Measurement and KPI Validation (TMV) Working Group. It reports 6G KPIs from SNS JU projects, by providing definitions, target values, and context to shape the 6G vision. BeGREEN has contributed to this valuable white paper by providing inputs (project KPIs) and by participation of our manager, Mir Ghorraishi, as co-editor. Many thanks to fellow projects and editorial team for making this great report published.

BeGREEN values collaborations within the great community of 6G SNS projects and takes an active role in various related activities!

WHITE PAPER
**6G KPIS – DEFINITIONS AND
TARGET VALUES**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1462968
URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1462968>

SNS JU Test Measurement and Validation WG

White Paper

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2.3 Scientific publications

The publications achieved during the latest months of the project are described in the following subsections, following a chronological order, and are 10 journal papers and 17 conference papers.

2.3.1 Journal paper at Computer Networks

The paper “Space and time user distribution measurements dataset in a university campus” by Olga Ruiz, Juan Sánchez-González, Jordi Pérez-Romero, Oriol Sallent, Irene Vilà, (UPC), has been accepted to Computer Networks, Volume 243, 2024, 110329, ISSN 1389-1286. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

“Radio Resource Management (RRM) strategies are essential components in mobile wireless networks, such as Long Term Evolution (LTE) or 5G New Radio (NR)[1]. The design of RRM algorithmic solutions is an area of research that has received a lot of attention for decades (see e.g. surveys [2–4] and references therein). Given that RRM strategies need to handle traffic dynamicity in the Radio Access Network (RAN), the availability of realistic user distributions in space and time can be very useful to support a more realistic performance assessment of RRM solutions. For this purpose, this article introduces a dataset containing real measurements of the number of users connected to the different Wi-Fi Access Points (APs) at the Campus Nord facilities of the *Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya* (UPC) in Barcelona. The Wi-Fi network is composed of 247 APs. To characterize the temporal variations, the data was collected for each AP every 1000 s (approximately) during 62 days. Besides the number of users connected to each AP (including users connected to both 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz bands), the dataset also contains information about the theoretical coverage area of each AP, so that the number of users connected to each AP can be associated to a specific geographical area. In this way, the dataset captures the spatio-temporal variations of users in the Campus at different times of the day, different days of the week and different periods of the academic year.”

2.3.2 Journal paper at IEEE Internet Computing

The paper “Open Experimental Measurements of Sub-6GHz Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces” by Marco Rossanese, Placido Mursia, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, Vincenzo Sciancalepore, Arash Asadi, Xavier Costa-Perez

(NEC/i2cat), has been accepted to IEEE Internet Computing Mar.-Apr. 2024, pp. 19-28, vol. 28. The abstract is:

“In this article, we present two datasets that we make publicly available for research. The data is collected in a testbed comprised of a custom-made reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) prototype and two regular orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) transceivers within an anechoic chamber. First, we discuss the details of the testbed and equipment used, including insights about the design and implementation of our RIS prototype. We further present the methodology we employ to gather measurement samples, which consists of letting the RIS electronically steer the signal reflections from an OFDM transmitter toward a specific location. To this end, we evaluate a suitably designed configuration codebook and collect measurement samples of the received power with an OFDM receiver. Finally, we present the resulting datasets, their format, and examples of exploiting this data for research purposes.”

2.3.3 Conference paper at AAAI 2024

The paper “Risk-Aware Continuous Control with Neural Contextual Bandits” by Jose A. Ayala-Romero, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, and Xavier Costa-Perez, has been accepted at the 38th Annual AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence 2024. The abstract is:

“Recent advances in learning techniques have garnered attention for their applicability to a diverse range of real-world sequential decision-making problems. Yet, many practical applications have critical constraints for operation in real environments. Most learning solutions often neglect the risk of failing to meet these constraints, hindering their implementation in real-world contexts. In this paper, we propose a risk-aware decision-making framework for contextual bandit problems, accommodating constraints and continuous action spaces. Our approach employs an actor multi-critic architecture, with each critic characterizing the distribution of performance and constraint metrics. Our framework is designed to cater to various risk levels, effectively balancing constraint satisfaction against performance. To demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach, we first compare it against state-of-the-art baseline methods in a synthetic environment, highlighting the impact of intrinsic environmental noise across different risk configurations. Finally, we evaluate our framework in a real-world use case involving a 5G mobile network where only our approach consistently satisfies the system constraint (a signal processing reliability target) with a small performance toll (8.5% increase in power consumption).”

2.3.4 Journal paper at IEEE Network

The paper “Enabling Beyond-Visual-Line-of-Sight Drones Operation over Open RAN 5G Networks with Slicing” by Pau Baguer, Esteban Municio, Gines Garcia-Aviles, and Xavier Costa-Perez, was published at *IEEE Network*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 163-169, Nov. 2024. The abstract is:

“Among the foretold claims of the transition from 5G to 6G, Beyond-Visual-Line-of-Sight (BVLoS) drone operation has emerged as a prominent Internet-of-Robots enabler. However, safety concerns have been raised since BVLoS imposes strict requirements on performance and dependability on the technology, and requires robust regulatory frameworks. While current 5G technologies promise to meet the performance requirements in terms of throughput and latency, there is a lack of studies regarding how to achieve full reliability in practice. To address this challenge, the research community is actively working on open-source projects that allow for experimental validation in the field. Fortunately, new Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) standards are paving the way for such approaches in an integrated, native manner. In this work, we deploy a state-of-the-art 5G O-RAN open-source BVLoS operational system, report current limitations, and address them via advanced

capabilities natively available in O-RAN: Slicing. Our proposed deployment minimizes trajectory errors due to 5G link congestion and keeps latency well below the 3GPP limits defined for BVLoS operation. Finally, we discuss on the challenges ahead and the opportunities that 5G O-RAN-enabled networks may bring to BVLoS drone operation.”

2.3.5 Conference paper at EuCNC 2024

The paper “BeGREEN Intelligent Plane for AI-driven Energy Efficient O-RAN management” by M. Catalan-Cid, J. Pueyo, J. Sanchez-Gonzalez, J. Gutierrez and M. Ghoraiishi, was presented at the Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit), Antwerp, Belgium, June 2024. The paper describes the BeGREEN Intelligent Plane developed in WP 4. The abstract is:

“Cellular networks are undergoing a revolutionary transform with the advent of O-RAN architectures and AI/ML solutions. O-RAN’s Non-Real-Time and Near-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controllers open the door to the implementation of automated control-loops that can provide RAN optimisations in numerous scenarios and use cases, and which can be further empowered by AI-driven approaches. Energetic sustainability has raised as one of the main optimisations targets due to the impact of mobile networks on global energy consumption. To this end, the BeGREEN project aims at enhancing the energy efficiency of beyond 5G networks by defining novel AI/ML-based methods at RAN and edge infrastructure. This paper presents BeGREEN Intelligent Plane, a novel framework which implements and exposes AI/ML workflows to O-RAN-based optimisations targeting energy efficiency. We also describe an exemplary application of the Intelligent Plane and its AI Engine, which aims at providing AI-driven cell on/off control.”

2.3.6 Conference paper at MeditCom 2024

The paper “Assessment of Energy Savings in Relay-Assisted 5G and Beyond Radio Access Networks” by J. Pérez-Romero, O. Ruiz, and O. Sallent, was published at the IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom), Madrid, Spain, July 2024. The paper is related to UPC’s work in WP 2 where the energy efficiency improvements and energy savings that can be achieved through the use of relays were analysed. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

“Reducing the overall energy consumption in mobile networks is currently an important aspect that drives the evolution towards 5G and beyond systems, both for environmental and economic reasons. In this direction, the use of relay nodes, whose interest is recently revamping through different initiatives such as the Integrated Access and Backhaul, is considered because they can contribute to reducing the overall power consumption thanks to improving the overall coverage conditions in the network. Then, this paper presents an assessment of the energy efficiency improvements and energy savings that can be achieved through the use of relays considering a realistic scenario of a university campus. The paper studies the different aspects that influence on these energy savings, such as the required bit rates and the power consumption model parameters.”

2.3.7 Journal paper at IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society

The paper “Attacking O-RAN Interfaces: Threat Modeling, Analysis and Practical Experimentation” by Pau Baguer, Girma M Yilma, Esteban Municio, Gines Garcia-Aviles, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, Marco Liebsch, and Xavier Costa-Pérez, was accepted in IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society, vol. 5, pp. 4559-4577, July 2024. The abstract is:

“A new generation of open and disaggregated Radio Access Networks (RANs) enabling multi-vendor, flexible, and cost-effective deployments is being promoted by the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Alliance. However, this new level of disaggregation in the RAN also entails new security risks that

must be carefully addressed. The O-RAN Alliance has established Working Group 11 (WG11) to ensure that the new specifications are secure by design. Acknowledging the new security challenges arising from the expanded threat surface, O-RAN WG11 provides procedures to identify threats and assess and mitigate risks. Reportedly, as of 2024, 60% of found risks are related to Denial of Service (DoS) and performance degradation. Therefore, in this work, we analyse a vanilla O-RAN deployment and evaluate the endurance of different O-RAN interfaces under attacks in scenarios involving DoS and performance degradation. To do so, we use a reference O-RAN open source deployment to report, risks found, weak points, and counter-intuitive recommended design choices for both control plane (A1, E2, and F1-c) and user plane (F1-u) interfaces. Consequently, we map O-RAN WG11's threat model and risk assessment methodology to our considered DoS and performance degradation scenarios, and dissect existing threats and potential attacks over O-RAN interfaces that may compromise the security of O-RAN architectural deployments. Finally, we identify mechanisms to mitigate risks and discuss approaches aimed at improving the robustness of future O-RAN networks."

2.3.8 Conference paper at INFOCOM 2024

The paper "YinYangRAN: Resource Multiplexing in GPU-Accelerated Virtualized RANs" by L. L. Schiavo, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Fiore and X. Costa-Perez, was accepted at IEEE INFOCOM 2024 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, Vancouver, BC, Canada, May 2024. The abstract is:

"RAN virtualization is revolutionizing the telco industry, enabling 5G Distributed Units to run using general-purpose platforms equipped with Hardware Accelerators (HAs). Recently, GPUs have been proposed as HAs, hinging on their unique capability to execute 5G PHY operations efficiently while also processing Machine Learning (ML) workloads. While this ambivalence makes GPUs attractive for cost-effective deployments, we experimentally demonstrate that multiplexing 5G and ML workloads in GPUs is in fact challenging, and that using conventional GPU-sharing methods can severely disrupt 5G operations. We then introduce YinYangRAN, an innovative O-RAN-compliant solution that supervises GPU-based HAs so as to ensure reliability in the 5G processing pipeline while maximizing the throughput of concurrent ML services. YinYangRAN performs GPU resource allocation decisions via a computationally-efficient approximate dynamic programming technique, which is informed by a neural network trained on real-world measurements. Using workloads collected in real RANs, we demonstrate that YinYangRAN can achieve over 50% higher 5G processing reliability than conventional GPU sharing models with minimal impact on co-located ML workloads. To our knowledge, this is the first work identifying and addressing the complex problem of HA management in emerging GPU-accelerated vRANs, and represents a promising step towards multiplexing PHY and ML workloads in mobile networks."

2.3.9 Conference paper at INFOCOM 2024

The paper "Mean-Field Multi-Agent Contextual Bandit for Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation in vRANs" by J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Lo Schiavo, A. Garcia-Saavedra and X. Costa-Perez, was accepted at IEEE INFOCOM 2024 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, Vancouver, BC, Canada, May 2024. The abstract is:

"Radio Access Network (RAN) virtualization, key for new-generation mobile networks, requires Hardware Accelerators (HAs) that swiftly process wireless signals from Base Stations (BSs) to meet stringent reliability targets. However, HAs are expensive and energy-hungry, which increases costs and has serious environmental implications. To address this problem, we gather data from our experimental platform and compare the performance and energy consumption of a HA (NVIDIA GPU V100) vs. a CPU (Intel Xeon Gold 6240R, 16 cores) for energy-friendly software processing. Based on the insights obtained from this data, we devise a strategy to offload workloads to HAs opportunistically to save energy while preserving reliability. This offloading strategy, however, needs to be configured

in near-real-time for every BS sharing common computational resources. This renders a challenging multi-agent collaborative problem in which the number of involved agents (BSs) can be arbitrarily large and can change over time. Thus, we propose an efficient multi-agent contextual bandit algorithm called ECORAN1, which applies concepts from mean field theory to be fully scalable. Using a real platform and traces from a production mobile network, we show that ECORAN can provide up to 40% energy savings with respect to the approach used today by the industry.”

2.3.10 Conference paper at ICMLCN 2024

The paper “MemorAI: Energy-Efficient Last-Level Cache Memory Optimization for Virtualized RANs” by E. S. Hidalgo, J. Xavier Salvat Lozano, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Li and X. Costa-Perez, was accepted at IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning for Communication and Networking (ICMLCN), Stockholm, Sweden, May 2024. The abstract is:

“The virtualization of Radio Access Networks (vRAN) is well on its way to become a reality, driven by its advantages such as flexibility and cost-effectiveness. However, virtualization comes at a high price — virtual Base Stations (vBSs) sharing the same computing platform incur a significant computing overhead due to in extremis consumption of shared cache memory resources. Consequently, vRAN suffers from increased energy consumption, which fuels the already high operational costs in 5G networks. This paper investigates cache memory allocation mechanisms’ effectiveness in reducing total energy consumption. Using an experimental vRAN platform, we profile the energy consumption and CPU utilization of vBS as a function of the network state (e.g., traffic demand, modulation scheme). Then, we address the high dimensionality of the problem by decomposing it per vBS, which is possible thanks to the Last-Level Cache (LLC) isolation implemented in our system. Based on this, we train a vBS digital twin, which allows us to train offline a classifier, avoiding the performance degradation of the system during training. Our results show that our approach performs very closely to an offline optimal oracle, outperforming standard approaches used in today’s deployments.”

This publication by BeGREEN partners NEC and i2cat was accepted into the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning for Communication and Networking!

2.3.11 Conference paper at IAICT 2024

The paper “Pre-Emptive Conflict Detection Architecture for O-RAN Service Management and Orchestration” by J. Armstrong, E. Fallon and S. Fallon, was accepted at IEEE International Conference on Industry 4.0, Artificial Intelligence, and Communications Technology (IAICT), BALI, Indonesia, July 2024. The abstract is:

“The evolution of telecommunications networks from closed to open architectures has led to the development of the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) standard. O-RAN’s Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) typically contains multiple autonomic management agents that simultaneously make configuration changes to optimize aspects of the network. Dealing with competing and conflicting configuration changes from these autonomic management agents remains a major issue. This paper proposes an extension to the O-RAN SMO architecture to incorporate a component that can predict when configuration changes are likely to degrade network performance. The purpose of this approach is to safeguard the actions taken by the management agents against unintended effects. The approach involves the use of two levels of clustering based on cell similarity and cell configuration. The results consist of predictions of network performance degradation based on statistical correlation with network performance.”

2.3.12 Journal paper at IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing

The paper “AegisRAN: A Fair and Energy-Efficient Computing Resource Allocation Framework for vRANs” by

Ethan Sanchez Hidalgo, Jose A. Ayala-Romero, J. Xavier Salvat Lozano, Andres Garcia-Saavedra and Xavier Costa Perez, was published in IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, April 2025. The abstract is:

“The virtualization of Radio Access Networks (vRAN) is rapidly becoming a reality, driven by the increasing need for flexible, scalable, and cost-effective mobile network solutions. To mitigate energy efficiency concerns in vRAN deployments, two approaches are gaining attention: (i) sharing computing infrastructure among multiple virtualized base stations (vBSs); and (ii) relying upon general-purpose, low-cost CPUs. However, effectively realizing these approaches poses several challenges. In this paper, we first conduct a comprehensive experimental campaign on a vRAN platform to characterize the impact of computing and radio resource allocation on energy consumption and performance across various network contexts. This analysis reveals several key issues. First, determining the optimal allocation of computing resources is difficult because it depends on the context of each vBS (e.g., traffic load, channel quality) in a non-trivial and non-linear manner. Second, suboptimal resource assignment can lead to increased energy consumption or, even worse, degradation of users' Quality of Service. Third, the high dimensionality of the solution space hinders the effectiveness of traditional optimization or learning methods. To tackle these challenges, we propose AegisRAN, a framework for optimizing computing resource allocation in vRAN. AegisRAN addresses the dual objective of minimizing energy consumption while maintaining high system reliability. Moreover, when computing resources are overbooked, our solution ensures a fair resource partition based on vBS performance. AegisRAN leverages a discrete soft actor-critic algorithm combined with several techniques, including multi-step decision-making, action masking, digital twin-based training, and a tailored reward signal that mitigates feedback sparsity. Our evaluations demonstrate that AegisRAN achieves near-optimal performance and offers high flexibility across diverse network contexts and varying numbers of vBSs, with up to 25% improvement in energy savings compared to baseline solutions in medium-scale scenarios.”

2.3.13 Conference paper at INFOCOM 2025

The paper "Kairos: Energy-Efficient Radio Unit Control for O-RAN via Advanced Sleep Modes", by J. X. Salvat Lozano, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra and X. Costa-Perez, was accepted at IEEE INFOCOM 2025 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, London, United Kingdom, May 2025. The abstract is:

“The high energy footprint of 5G base stations, particularly the radio units (RUs), poses a significant environmental and economic challenge. We introduce Kairos, a novel approach to maximize the energy-saving potential of O-RAN's Advanced Sleep Modes (ASMs). Unlike state-of-the-art solutions, which often rely on complex ASM selection algorithms unsuitable for time-constrained base stations and fail to guarantee stringent QoS demands, Kairos offers a simple yet effective joint ASM selection and radio scheduling policy capable of real-time operation. This policy is then optimized using a data-driven algorithm within an xApp, which enables several key innovations: (i) a dimensionality-invariant encoder to handle variable input sizes (e.g., time-varying network slices), (ii) distributional critics to accurately model QoS metrics and ensure constraint satisfaction, and (iii) a single-actor-multiple-critic architecture to effectively manage multiple constraints. Through experimental analysis on a commercial RU and trace-driven simulations, we demonstrate Kairos's potential to achieve energy reductions ranging between 15% and 72% while meeting QoS requirements, offering a practical solution for cost- and energy-efficient 5G networks.”

2.3.14 Conference paper at INFOCOM 2025

The paper "FairRIC: Real-time Fair Allocation in O-RAN with Shared Computing", by F. Aslan, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez and G. Iosifidis, was accepted at IEEE INFOCOM 2025 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, London, United Kingdom, May 2025. The abstract is:

“The deployment of O-RAN systems on general-purpose computing platforms represents a significant paradigm shift, promising remarkable performance improvements. However, these architectures may potentially increase both the capital and operational expenses of the network. The processor pooling concept is a promising solution to address this problem, consisting of a set of processing units (PUs) in the O-Cloud shared by several virtualized BSs (vBSs). Nevertheless, this strategy requires sophisticated resource assignment mechanisms to provide the expected gains in terms of cost and reliability. This paper proposes a novel online learning framework that assigns computing resources to vBSs in real-time (e.g., every TTI), thus handling the burstiness of real traffic loads. Our algorithm relies on online convex optimization (OCO) theory, extending state-of-the-art approaches in long-term fairness and constrained optimization and allowing discrete decisions. Our method offers an intrinsic closed-form iteration, speeding up the computation process and consequently allowing real-time operation. Moreover, our solution has guarantees in terms of fairness among the vBSs while adhering to long-term energy constraints over the entire operation horizon. We validate our theoretical findings via simulation and evaluate experimentally the algorithms in an O-RAN platform.”

2.3.15 Demo at INFOCOM 2025

The demo "Demo: BeGREEN Intelligence Plane for AI-driven Energy Efficient O-RAN management", by Miguel Catalan-Cid, German Castellanos, David Reiss, Joss Armstrong, was presented at IEEE INFOCOM 2025 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, London, United Kingdom, May 2025. The abstract is:

“Cellular networks management is being enhanced by O-RAN architecture and AI/ML solutions, enabling automated intelligent control loops for RAN optimization across various use cases. Ensuring energy sustainability is crucial to minimizing the impact of mobile networks on global energy consumption. This demo showcases the BeGREEN Intelligence Plane, an AI-driven solution for energy-efficient management of O-RAN networks. The presented workflow focuses on controlling the operational status of emulated cells, highlighting the integration of key components such as the AI Engine and the optimizations achieved through rApps and xApps.”

2.3.16 Conference paper at ICC 2025

The paper “Quantifying the Energy-Saving and QoS Trade-Off in Traffic Offloading for Real 4G/5G Scenarios” by D. Reiss, M. Catalan-Cid, D. Camps Mur, and J.O. Sallent Roig, was accepted at IEEE International Conference on Communications 2025 - Fourth International Workshop on Green and Sustainable Networking: GreenNet'25 (ICC GreenNet'25), Canada, June 2025. They won the Best Paper award. The abstract is:

“Despite the potential for higher energy efficiency in 5G networks, current 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) deployments often operate suboptimally due to low utilization of 4G and 5G carriers during extended periods. Since base stations are the primary contributors to network energy consumption, implementing cell on/off switching and traffic offloading strategies is crucial for enhancing energy efficiency in current deployments. This paper investigates energy-saving opportunities based on these strategies in a real 5G NSA deployment, utilizing a dataset provided by a European Mobile Network Operator. Using Key Performance Indicators from the dataset, we propose a data-driven framework to evaluate the energy-saving and QoS trade-off when selectively deactivating underutilized 5G cells and offloading their traffic to 4G cells with enough resources within the same sector and site. Our results demonstrate network-wide cell switch-off opportunities ranging from 17% to 79%, while ensuring data rates between 25 Mbps and 5 Mbps, respectively.”

2.3.17 Conference paper at EuCNC 2025

The paper “Comparative Analysis of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces and Relay Nodes for Energy Saving” by Jordi Pérez-Romero, J. Xavier Salvat Lozano, Jose A. Ayala-Romero, Oriol Sallent, Anna Umbert, and Juan Sánchez-González, was accepted at 2025 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit), Poznan, Poland, June 2025. The abstract is:

“Different technologies are currently being investigated to reduce the energy consumption of beyond 5 G systems. Two of the most preeminent ones are the Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) and the relays, as both of them allow reducing the overall transmitted power levels at the base stations. However, due to the different nature of the two approaches, RISs being mostly passive while relays being active devices, it is unclear in which conditions one or the other leads to higher energy savings. This paper intends to shed light on this question by presenting a thorough analytical study of both approaches. Compared to the current literature, this study goes a step further by considering a more accurate RIS modeling based on actual RIS equipment, a thorough comparison of different energy consumption models, and a comprehensive study in a realistic environment of a university campus including indoor and outdoor propagation.”

2.4 Organizing highly directed workshops

BeGREEN members are very active and feature a vast expertise in organising flagship conference workshops and special sessions in the technical areas of the project. For example, members of the project organized workshops in the last three EuCNCs. Following this consolidated strategy, BeGREEN is taking the lead in organizing international workshops in collaboration with other projects, as a premiere opportunity to present project results in a very interactive and formal environment.

2.4.1 Workshops and booths for EuCNC 2025

2.4.1.1 Presentation of ISAC activities Special Session 6

This session³ featured four presentations from leading European projects in the ISAC domain: INSTINCT, MULTIX, 6G-DISAC, and BeGREEN, showcasing their latest findings and advancements in ISAC. The session investigates the potential of ISAC to revolutionize various applications, including autonomous driving, smart cities, industrial automation, and extended reality, by offering enhanced situational awareness, resource efficiency, and novel service capabilities. Contributions addressing theoretical frameworks, innovative algorithms, experimental prototypes, and standardization efforts related to ISAC are highly encouraged, aiming to pave the way for its seamless integration into future wireless ecosystems, with the insights shared from these key European initiatives providing valuable perspectives on the current state-of-the-art and future directions.

2.4.1.2 Panel discussion on “Sixtustainability: Solid Technologies for a Green 6G”

Our BeGREEN rProject Manager, Dr. Mir Ghoraishi, chaired an exciting expert panel discussion on “Sixtustainability: Solid Technologies for a Green 6G” at EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025 in Poznan. This panel brought together top minds from academia, industry, and policy to explore how we can make next-generation networks both high-performing and environmentally responsible. The experts participating in the panel were: Ali Rezaki (Nokia), Anastasius Gavras (Eurescom), Artur Hecker (Huawei), Mays AL-Naday, Chiara Lombardo (CNIT, University of Genova), Monique Calisti (Martel), Stefan Wendt (Orange), moderated by Mir Ghoraishi;

³ <https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/special-sessions/special-session-6/>

Key topics included:

- How can innovation and sustainability go hand in hand?
- Which technologies and architectures can drive Energy Efficient, green networks?
- For a holistic approach toward a sustainable 6G, how to rethink the architecture, business models, hardware, and Social Values?

2.4.1.3 EuCNC 2025 Workshop: Technology Enablers for Sustainable 6G Design

See: <https://www.sns-begreen.com/news/eucnc-2025-workshop-on-technology-enablers-for-sustainable-6g-design>

This workshop is proposed by collecting contributions from 17 SNS projects, SNS Sustainability Task Force, and 6G-IA Vision Working Group. Their representatives in the event will be sharing their views, achievements, and lessons learnt from their respective projects. The current state of the art fuelled by the insights from the SNS JU projects and the sustainability targets, methodologies and indicators currently employed by these projects as well as the trade-offs, gaps, lessons learned and challenges experienced, analysed in the SNS Sustainability Task Force, will be introduced; and the recent white paper recently released by 6G-IA Vision Working Group will be discussed. The collected insights from each of these activities will be presented in a dedicated session. The expert panel discussion in the end of the day will provide further interaction and alignment on the issue, toward the conclusion and wrap up of the workshop. The contributors are committed to boost the dissemination of workshop conclusions and findings by bringing them into future activities that they organise on a regular basis

Figure 2-10 “Technology Enablers for Sustainable 6G Design” Workshop @ EuCNC 2025

2.4.1.4 “Sustainability for 6G” Exhibitor

See: <https://www.sns-begreen.com/news/eucnc-2025-joint-booth-on-sustainability-for-6g-from-infrastructure-to-services>

This EUCNC’25 exhibition booth, organized by BeGREEN, provided an in-depth presentation of five selected SNS projects, notably BeGREEN, 6G-TWIN, 6GREEN, EXIGENCE, and 6G-SENSES, that are explicitly targeting concrete ecological improvements of 6G, going from energy efficiency over carbon footprint reduction to net energy consumption limitation.

Hence, each of the participating projects addresses specific challenges, yet the presented solutions are complementary in that they exhibit strong potential for synergetic integration on a system level. Together, these projects therefore could contribute concrete and quantifiable improvements towards an overall more sustainable 6G. Common to all involved projects is the strong shared belief that the technology improvement will have the strongest network effect, therefore positively influencing other aspects, such as economic and societal sustainability, in a longer run.

In this sense, the presented demos cover different aspects, ranging from RAN energy efficiency enhancement by introducing RAN (and network) monitoring and optimisation, over new architectures and enablers for improving energy efficiency of the future network, i.e., Cell-Free MIMO and Integrated Communication and Sensing, a proposed Observability Framework for monitoring energy consumption of the physical and virtual components of the network, to green, live ecolabels for future 6G services, empowering service users and incentivising them to an ecologically-aware usage.

BeGREEN showcased the Intelligence Plane Demo live (Figure 2-12), which showcased the baseline implementation of the Intelligence Plane, concretely the AI Engine and the non-RT, integrated with the dRAX and Emulated RAN via VIAVI TeraVM AI RAN Scenario Generator (RSG). The AI Engine will host two ML models, a cell load predictor, and a cell energy predictor, already trained with offline data. Then, “AI Engine Assist rApps/xApps” will be deployed in the RICs to assist ML model inference, exposed to a control rApp. Finally, a RAN control action based on the ML model output will be sent to the dRAX and the Emulated RAN, so action could be seen in real time. Visitors will see the results on a specific Grafana dashboard to showcase the different outputs of the demo. Here, the A1 policies created by the rApp and their implication on the Project KPI such Energy Score and Power consumption reduction was presented.

The EuCNC booth was visited by the SNS-JU delegation.

Figure 2-11 SNS-JU visit to “Sustainability for 6G” booth @ EuCNC 2025

Figure 2-12 Intelligence Plane Demo showcased at EuCNC'25

2.5 Participation in 5G/B5G initiatives

The members of the consortium have been, and are very active, in organizing activities related to the BeGREEN research areas. These constitute very important forums for presenting the achieved results to the scientific and industrial communities. Similarly, the BeGREEN project members are highly involved in international programme committees and editorial boards of key conferences and journals. BeGREEN members' participation in joint initiatives among related projects in the ICT program is anticipated. BeGREEN has already taken the initiative to make a cluster of related topic projects to boost publicising the project activities and the dissemination of the results.

2.5.1 Expert Panel Discussion at CSCN 2024

Several SNS projects (BeGREEN, 6GREEN and EXIGENCE) took part in the “Operational Sustainability of 6G Systems” Panel discussion at the IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (IEEE CSCN 2024) event. From BeGREEN side, BeGREEN Project Manager, Dr. Mir Ghoraihi, spoke at the panel discussion providing our insights on the topic.

2.6 Industry exhibitions

The project has been actively searching for opportunities to present project findings. BeGREEN brochures were shared at the booth of consortium partners at Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2024 and MWC 2025. Partners who have a booth at MWC and have their booth available for BeGREEN brochure are: Accelleran, RunEL, Parallel Wireless, i2CAT (QR code and logo), ARM (QR code and logo). The SNS JU community is informed regarding BeGREEN plan for MWC presence.

2.6.1 Globecom 2024 Industry Panel

Dr. Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS), Project Manager of BeGREEN, spoke at the Globecom Industry Panel IPA-03 on “Green-Native Design: Path Toward Sustainable 6G”, alongside Dr. Artur Hecker from Huawei, Dr. Emmanuel Dotaro of Thales, Prof. Maziar Nekovee from The University of Sussex and Dr. Sebastian Robitzsch of InterDigital, Inc.

The main discussion was centred around the integration of more sustainable mobile networks, aiming at net-zero targets. He also covered different approaches and solutions, as well as discussing how artificial intelligence can help the industry achieve these goals, and what the cost would be to employ such solutions!

2.6.2 MWC 2025

Find more on SNS BeGREEN Project and project demos showcased at MWC 2025:

- 1) **BeGREEN Intelligence Plane** - dRAX Integration demo. Accelleran demonstrates the BeGREEN Intelligence Plane, showcasing hashtag#A1 policies for energy savings, multivendor integration, and harmonic telemetry processing. This solution delivers real-time energy optimization in ORAN networks, achieving up to 40% energy savings without impacting network quality.
- 2) **Power Amplifier Blanking for B5G Radio Unit (RU)**, as well as the module architecture, its operating mode, and the RU power consumption savings that can be achieved out of this module.

2.7 Dissemination through training and personal mobility

BeGREEN will increase the number of students trained in the areas covered by the project. MSc or PhD students working in the project will carry their ideas into their future workplaces and academic institutions, thus increasing the reach of BeGREEN impact.

2.8 Datasets published

The information associated to this section has been provided in deliverable D4.4 “Data sets used to train AI/ML models”.

3 External Liaison

3.1 Participation in SNS JU

BeGREEN partners and delegates have been active in collaboration with other SNS and 6G IA projects in the framework of the Collaboration Agreement. In such framework the information exchange and other sorts of interactions with peer projects are easily achievable. BeGREEN consortium is experienced as they have been active in the community for the past years in 5G-PPP projects. This active liaison with SNS activities and the interactions with other projects within this framework is led by the BeGREEN Project Manager.

The project has representation in the Steering Board (SB) and Technology Board and contribute fully to the actions emanating from these fora.

3.1.1 Participation in SNS Working Groups

Participants to the WGs are listed in Table 3-1. The activities of these WGs are formalised in fortnightly, or monthly, WG meetings. These might include project presentations, joint white paper preparations, joint event (e.g., workshop, panel, etc.) proposals, and so on.

Table 3-1 BeGREEN Consortium Participation in SNS WGs

Working Group	Participants	Specific contribution made (if any)
Architecture	GIGASYS, LMI, NEC, ACC	
Reliable software networks	ACC	
Test, Measurements and Validation	TSA, GIGASYS	
Sustainability TF (now WG)	GIGASYS, IHP	The PM and TMs of BeGREEN led a chapter in the preparation of the SNS JU White Paper Chapter entitled "Sustainability in SNS JU Projects: Targets, Methodologies, Trade-offs and Implementation Considerations Towards 6G Systems" ⁴
Hardware Technologies	IHP	Participation in the first two calls, Working Group set up late for BeGREEN to contribute

3.1.2 Participation to 6G-IA WGs

As it is observed in Table 3-2, the project already has representatives in most of the 6G-IA WGs to channelise the project contributions, and in occasions, edit position papers, deliverables and reports from the working groups, proactively driving WGs closely related to their project goals.

Table 3-2 BeGREEN Consortium Participation in 6G-IA WGs

Working Group	Participants	Specific contribution made (if any)
5G for CAM	-	
Open Smart Networks and Services	GIGASYS, I2CAT, LMI, TSA, NEC, REL	
Pre-Standardization	TSA, NEC, GIGASYS	
Security	TSA, GIGASYS, ACC	

⁴ https://smart-networks.europa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/sns_ju_sustainabilitytf_whp_june2025_v1.0-1.pdf

Trials	GIGASYS, LMI	
Vision and Societal Challenges	TSA	
Women in Telecommunications and Research	-	

4 Innovation Goals and Methodology

The innovation potential of the results of BeGREEN are presented in this section, where we provide the Innovation assessment of Period 2. This is aligned with the contributions to be made to the Innovation Radar, where we will identify high-potential innovators and innovations and their specific 'go to market' needs ultimately encourage and support innovators in getting their innovations 'out of the lab' and into (or at least closer to) the market.

Following the methodology described in BeGREEN deliverable D6.2 [3], we carried out the exercise per technical WP.

- **WP2:** In WP2, BeGREEN proposed an evolved radio network that targets not only improved wireless communication's efficiency by maximising performance but also reducing energy consumption. BeGREEN D2.1 [7] delved into describing current energy efficient frameworks and strategies that aim to model the radio access network (RAN) that serve for identifying and quantifying the parts of this network segment that can allow for improved energy efficiency and reduced energy consumption. We provided an initial description of the proposed UCs and their specific requirements, focusing on the scenarios that are subject to study and the reference Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be later evaluated and captured in subsequent BeGREEN documents, together with a high-level analysis of the BeGREEN RAN architecture along with the optimization strategies that can be applied to the RAN components. BeGREEN D2.1 [7] also provided the energy control mechanisms that can be applied in a 5G disaggregated RAN and mechanisms enhanced by artificial intelligence and/or machine learning (AI/ML). A key innovation of BeGREEN will be providing energy efficiency ratings and energy scores through the Energy Efficiency Calculation rApps, this is being discussed as part of WP2 and WP4 work. BeGREEN D2.2 [8] evolved this initial architecture, reporting the further architectural work of WP2 and evaluation in D2.3 [9].
- **WP3:** In WP3, BeGREEN addresses multiple physical layer enhancements and new technologies that will enable improving the energy efficiency of the RAN for future wireless mobile networks. Additionally, the use of these new technologies for further enhancement of the overall network energy efficiency was investigated. This was reported in BeGREEN D3.1 [10] and BeGREEN D3.2 [5], with the final evaluation and benchmarking in BeGREEN D3.3 [11].

The work in WP3 is performed in different levels and segments of the RAN. The main reasoning behind this approach is that not all the segments have the same potential for energy efficiency optimization. Therefore, within the first period of the project (BeGREEN D3.1 [10]) the areas that have the highest potential for energy efficiency optimization as well as the possible strategies for optimization, were identified. This partially disperses the work of the different partners and limits the integration of the developed technologies. Nevertheless, their work was grouped around a few different approaches for improving the network energy efficiency, which is one of the main goals of the project.

Within the first reporting period, the potential for energy efficiency optimization of different segment of the RAN was investigated and potential areas as well as approaches were identified. This includes optimization of the channel coder/decoder, since it is one of the most energy intensive part of the DU. Additionally, CU energy consumption, as well as its potential for reducing its energy consumption was assessed. Furthermore, energy optimization approaches for the remote radio head (RRH) were identified and possible strategies proposed. Finally, it was investigated how new technologies like ISAC and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) can be used for improving the network energy efficiency. Additional information and initial results that endorse the work carried out in WP3 was reported in BeGREEN D3.2 [5].

- **WP4:** The Intelligence Plane, together with its components and interfaces, is one of the main innovations coming from WP4. The AI Engine, which exposes MLOps workflows to the RICs, could be of special interest to Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN Alliance)- aligned RIC vendors and costumers due to the actual trend of AI-driven RAN optimisations. Additionally, cross-domain AI approaches such as the one being proposed in BeGREEN, which incorporates data and optimisations from RAN, Edge, Core, Application and Sensing domains, are gaining relevance in the telecom sector [12]. In this regard, the integration of RIS/ISAC technologies and O-RAN is also of significant importance due to the relevance of these technologies in 6G definition. Finally, novel rApps/xApps proposed by BeGREEN will exploit these innovations to enhance network energy efficiency. Regarding O-RAN interfaces, we are now focusing on the A1 interface due to its versatility to incorporate policies, enrichment information and AI/ML-related workflows. This allow interaction, coordination, and conflict management between non-Real-Time (rApps) and near-Real-Time RICs (xApps), which are operations of special interest to effectively manage AI-driven automated control-loops. On the contrary, implementation-wise, the RU control through O1 interface has lost traction in the project since RunEL's RU does not incorporate this interface and their proposed RU optimisations do not require of a non-RT control. Also, in the integration with TeraVM RAN emulator we plan to focus on A1 and E2 interfaces for demonstrating intelligent and energy efficient RU management. The results of BeGREEN WP4 were reported in BeGREEN D4.1 [13] and BeGREEN D4.2 [6], with the final architecture and evaluation of the Intelligence Plane and AI/ML algorithms reported in BeGREEN D4.3 [14].

5 Exploitation Plans & Outcomes

5.1 Identification and classification of exploitation plans

The exploitable outcomes of BeGREEN include research results, products, and integrated demonstrators for specific use cases. The exploitable outcomes list and classification is summarized Table 5-1 with the corresponding owner(s).

Table 5-1 BeGREEN Exploitable Outcomes

#	Exploitation Outcome	Outcome Category	Methodology	Owners
1	RU power management (RU On/Off)	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	REL
2	RU power management (PA management)	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	REL
3	Intelligence Plane + TeraVM (RU On/Off)	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	ACC / I2CAT / LMI / BT
4	Intelligence Plane	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	ACC / I2CAT
5	Sensing-assisted communications	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	IHP / I2CAT / NEC
6	CU HW acceleration	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	ACC / ARM
7	RIC porting into ARM	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	ACC / ARM / I2CAT
8	DU HW acceleration	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	PW / ARM
9	ISAC / RIS	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	IHP / NEC / I2CAT
10	Saving modules such as Digital-Pre-Distortion (DPD), Envelope Tracking (ET) and Power Amplifier (PA) Blanking	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	RunEL
11	Development of rApps/xApps for optimizing Energy Efficiency in the RAN	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	I2CAT / ACC
12	CU / RIC HW acceleration. Develop xApps to achieve energy efficiently	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	ACC / I2CAT / ARM
13	DU HW Acceleration	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	PW
14	Assessment of energy savings in distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) scenaria	Research Achievement	Specific Exploitation Plan	TSA
15	Development of rApps/xApps for Relay management / Building NDT	Research Achievement	Specific Exploitation Plan	UPC

5.2 Individual exploitation plan

The individual consortium partners, all of which are committed to contribute according to their expertise and profile, have the following ambitions for exploitation of the results of BeGREEN project:

5.2.1 Industrial partners

5.2.1.1 BT

BT is both the operator of the largest public mobile network in the UK under the EE brand and has a BT Enterprise division that provides telecommunications services to other commercial organisations. BT Enterprise customers include other public Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) through the supply of backhaul/fronthaul connectivity and physical base-station infrastructure provision including neutral host. In addition, a growing market for private mobile networks is targeted by BT Enterprise. As a public operator, BT will use the output of BeGREEN to minimise power cost OPERational EXpenditures (OPEX) through energy efficiency. This will be achieved, where appropriate, by influencing standards and RAN equipment vendors, selecting equipment that meets the energy efficiency capability that will be established in BeGREEN and, through the availability of the RIC, deploying algorithms capable of optimising energy efficiency for the specific BT customer base. As a supplier to public and private network operators, BT will use the knowledge gained through BeGREEN to define new connectivity and telecommunication service products, including for example the deployment of RIS. The ability to provide energy-optimised solutions for private networks will also support growth of the BT market share. BT is also hopeful of applications of BeGREEN ideas to energy-saving in home Wi-Fi, a market sector in which BT is a very big player. Specifically, the use of Wi-Fi relays improves coverage but costs energy. Ways to choose the right trade-off should emerge from BeGREEN concepts.

<p>PROBLEM</p> <p>Energy management capabilities in O-RAN</p> <p>Energy management capabilities in home Wi-Fi</p> <p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>None</p>	<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>Integration of the BeGREEN Intelligence Plane into O-RAN architecture defining new interfaces and components</p> <p>KEY METRICS</p> <p><u>Power:</u> Energy, Power consumption</p> <p><u>Signal properties:</u> SINR, RSRP, MCS</p>	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION</p> <p>Small-cell deployments (coverage infill, indoor) with smart energy management.</p> <p>Home Wi-Fi relays with smart energy-efficient self-configuration.</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE</p> <p>Access to relevant datasets</p> <p>CHANNELS</p> <p>BT Business Units</p>	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <p>MNOs</p> <p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>TBD</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>TBD</p>		

The research arm of BT has been reorganized to focus on higher TRL technologies and solutions, closer to commercial markets, rather than lower TRL pure research. During the BeGREEN final demonstrations @ BT Adastral Park in June 2025, the results of BeGREEN were demonstrated to many colleagues in these reorganized research departments. There was significant interest in many of these results, with intentions to mature these results, in the scope of this reorganized higher TRL research organization, towards introduction into BT’s commercial systems in 2-4 years, where commercial advantages are determined.

5.2.1.2 Telefónica (TSA)

Telefónica (TSA) plans to use the knowledge acquired from BeGREEN in the definition of the future network architectures, with the focus on provisioning novel wireless services. It will also provide a realistic overview of the maturity of the different technological components that should be available, facilitating the

identification of cooperation opportunities to speed up their development. TSA plans to involve its industrial partners and stakeholders in the design of technically feasible and scalable commercial products from the project concepts. TSA will also explore new business opportunities in the private wireless networks based on positioning and cell-free network topologies, for example in factory environments or event locations.

Innovation:

Traditional MIMO has been used to improve data rate while reducing interference by creating narrow beams. However, traditional MIMO exhibits poor performance in the edge of the cell since the signal quality is limited and interference from other cells detrimentally affects the performance.

TSA provides a cell-free architecture and compares it with traditional MIMO to show in realistic 5G deployments how much energy an operator can save while providing better performance.

The value proposition is presented in the following VP and Lean Canvases

PROBLEM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficient RAN deployment complexity High CAPEX of network High OPEX of network EXISTING ALTERNATIVES none	SOLUTION Develop new network architectures that can use power more efficiently through the use of distributed radio heads	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION Radio densification.	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE -	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> private enterprises MNOs EARLY ADOPTERS Private networks
	KEY METRICS <u>Power:</u> Energy, Power consumption, IDLE PC. <u>Traffic:</u> Throughput, Max achievable throughput, CPU Load. <u>Aggregated:</u> Bits/Joules.		CHANNELS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturers Operators 	
COST STRUCTURE -		REVENUE STREAMS -		

5.2.1.3 Ericsson (LMI)

Ericsson is a world leader in developing a distributed network management solution for 5G, B5G and 6G

networks. In Ericsson Ireland, we are actively involved in research around B5G, 6G, orchestration, data analysis and automation. The results and knowledge which will be gained through our participation in BeGREEN will be exploited to (1) enhance internal know-how in the areas of automatic optimisations, data analytics, orchestration; (2) have a continuous role in collaborative European research projects; and (3) assess impact & improvements that we could bring towards our products.

Ericsson (LMI) will use BeGREEN results to foster the growth of its Innovation department focused on energy saving in future RAN developments. LMI have a goal to include the outcome of this project to promote energy efficiency in our development plans and new energy efficiency features in B5G and 6G as well as propose new standards in energy efficiency.

We will, throughout the duration of the project, disseminate our work and results in BeGREEN internally throughout our organization. This will be done through one-to-one discussions, department-level presentations, as well as major events such as Operational Support System (OSS) Tech Day, where participants from the various sites involved in OSS development in Ericsson are invited, together with our customers.

LMI individual exploitation plan

LMI will use BeGREEN results to foster the growth of its Innovation department focused on energy saving in future RAN developments.

LMI will use the outcome of this project to promote energy efficiency in our development plans.

LMI will use the outcome of this project to promote new energy efficiency features in B5G and 6G.

5.2.1.4 ARM

Despite the initial enthusiasm of leveraging ARM based chipsets into the disaggregated 5G RAN vendor ecosystem, and with ARM providing platforms for 5G RAN network function porting and energy consumption comparisons, they lost interest in participating in BeGREEN and did not request any later funding.

As with their competitors, like Intel with their vRAN AVX processor instruction set extensions, and GPU and other DSP type hardware acceleration (like NVIDIA Grace and NXP Layerscale) vendors, the volumes have

remained too low to be commercially interesting for them.

Compared to volumes of say M1/M4 chipsets for Apple Macs, A18 Bionic in iPhones, Samsung Exynos SoCs in their smartphones, the only volumes in the 4G/5G network supply have been through the large Ericsson/Nokia/Huawei vendors for PLMN, where Intel have a current dominance (Ericsson/Samsung locked into x86 and vRAN Boost accelerator for FEC) though they are trying to address that⁵⁶. The market for the entire chipset supply ecosystems, Like Intel NEX, is similarly struggling for viability⁷, with everyone pivoting to supplying the larger AI and datacenter markets.

With slower than anticipated ramp-up of Open RAN and Private 5G, the volumes to supply the disaggregated 5G RAN vendor eco-system markets are lower still

5.2.1.5 Parallel Wireless (PW)

PW is one of the pioneers in accelerating the global O-RAN movement, building wireless networks around the world with their in-house software and hardware solutions. BeGREEN output will be used by PW for significant simplification in terms of cost and power consumption focusing on effective solutions, specifically for the upcoming multiuser MIMO. PW intends to convert the vast majority of the PHY processing (which gets higher and higher with multiuser MIMO) to very low CPU consuming process with efficient GPU based acceleration. Accordingly, the results and based on the advanced outputs of BeGREEN, PW will develop and productize RU offload HW and SW solution and will make it commercially available leveraging best fit Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) GPU-based accelerators.

The exploitation plans of PW at then of the project are essentially unchanged, but tempered by the realities of the Open RAN solutions market.

5.2.1.6 NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH (NEC)

NEC plans to use the results and findings from BeGREEN to improve its current RIS product prototypes and evolve its data-driven product portfolio considering the benefits of AI and ML to optimize energy efficiency for AI services. In this way, BeGREEN will have an impact on NEC’s Mobile Radio Access Networks and Mobile Wireless Networking business units, specifically, on O-RAN compliant virtualized RAN products and NEC’s advanced analytics platform for next-generation OSS. The project results will be used to demonstrate how it is possible to leverage developed innovations to optimize the energy consumption to both NEC development groups and potential customers, e.g., European network operators.

PROBLEM	SOLUTION	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
RIS integration into O-RAN RIS reconfiguration using sensing	Integration of the RIS into the O-RAN architecture defining new interfaces and components Using ISAC metrics to reconfigure the RISs	AI-powered energy efficient RIS control that leverages sensing and physical layer measurements to reconfigure RISs	Novel AI/ML algorithms, access to relevant datasets	MNOs EARLY ADOPTERS

⁵ <https://www.lightreading.com/open-ran/arm-has-a-ran-plan-to-end-intel-lock-in-for-ericsson-and-samsung>

⁶ <https://www.lightreading.com/open-ran/ericsson-still-looks-armless-in-cloud-ran-with-intel-or-nothing>

⁷ <https://tecknexus.com/intel-spins-off-nex-division-amid-2-9b-loss-ai-pivot/>

EXISTING ALTERNATIVES RIS could be reconfigured using physical layer measurements from the DU Relays could be an alternative for RIS	KEY METRICS <u>Power:</u> Energy, Power consumption <u>Signal properties:</u> SINR, RSRP, MCS		CHANNELS NEC Business Units	Companies trying to adopt sell RIS solutions for MNOs adopting O-RAN
COST STRUCTURE TBD		REVENUE STREAMS TBD		

The innovation plans for NEC at the project end remains unchanged but as for all vendors, the market is challenging and are looking to leverage 3rd party ODM solutions into their portfolio to complement their own produced technologies and solutions⁸.

5.2.2 Research and academic partners

5.2.2.1 I2CAT Foundation (I2CAT)

i2CAT will focus its exploitation on the O-RAN related assets developed in the project such as the O-RAN Non-RT RIC and the developed rApps for optimizing energy efficiency in the RAN. Market exploitation of this software assets will be pursued through license transfer agreements.

In particular, I2CAT will disseminate relevant project results to the industrial sector, starting with the members of its board of trustees that include MNOs like Orange, Vodafone, Telefonica, and Parlem, and vendors like Juniper, Cisco and Fujitsu. In addition, I2CAT will also disseminate the relevant project results to the public administration of Catalonia that is fostering policies around digitalization. I2CAT is leading the connectivity strand of the DIH4CAT⁹, which is a digital innovation hub aimed at strengthening the digital competences of Catalan SME. Finally, Neutron¹⁰ is an I2CAT spin off developing a cloud-based management system for private 5G network. Neutron is thus a clear recipient of some of the innovations developed in BeGREEN. Project results will also foster i2CAT participation in future calls of the SNS program.

Innovation:

i2CAT will study joint intelligent control of RAN and RIS empowered by AI/ML. To do this, i2CAT will leverage the O-RAN architecture, re-using O-RAN interfaces and components and extending them whenever needed. This may include developing xApps/rApps and the definition of new service and information models for the E1 and O1 interfaces.

The proposed Intelligence Plane incorporates an AI Engine, which will provide a serverless execution environment hosting the AI/ML models, offering inference and training services to the rApps/xApps by following a loosely coupled approach. This solution allows ML model developers to focus on the model implementation and optimisation, while rApp developers can work on the control logic independently of how the model will be trained and served.

I2CAT individual exploitation plan

i2CAT developments within BeGREEN are focused on two main topics, which could be exploited as an asset:

⁸ <https://www.lightreading.com/open-ran/mavenir-and-nec-adjust-to-ran-realities>

⁹ <https://dih4cat.cat/en/>

¹⁰ <https://www.neutron.com/>

- Intelligence Plane: non-RT RIC implementation plus AI Engine to expose and facilitate AI/ML services to rApp developers. RIS Control integrated with O-RAN architecture.
- AI/ML-based RAN optimisations for energy efficiency:
 - Cell on/off control: rApp managing the on/off cycles of the cells in the RUs according to traffic predictions.
 - User Plane Function (UPF) CPU control: rApp managing the CPU state of edge COTS servers hosting UPFs according to traffic predictions.
 - RIS Control: rApp/xApp managing RIS to join coverage extension and cell on/off control.

The value proposition is presented in the following VP & Lean Canvases.

<p>PROBLEM</p> <p>AI/ML integration into O-RAN</p> <p>RIS integration into O-RAN</p> <p>Implementation of energy efficient optimisations for O-RANs</p>	<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>Intelligence Plane for EE RANs with integrates AI Engine to support AI/ML services and RIS Control</p> <p>AI/ML-based optimisations targeting energy-efficiency through RU control, RIS control and UPF CPU control</p>	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION</p> <p>AI-powered energy efficient RAN control that leverages CPU optimization, RU management and RIS control</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE</p> <p>Novel AI/ML algorithms, access to relevant datasets</p>	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <p>NPN providers</p> <p>MNOs</p> <p>RIC Vendors</p>
<p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>Existing RIC implementations and AI/ML frameworks</p> <p>Relays could be an alternative for RIS</p>	<p>KEY METRICS</p> <p><u>Power</u>: Energy, Power consumption</p> <p><u>Traffic</u>: Throughput, Max achievable throughput, CPU Load.</p> <p><u>Signal properties</u>: SINR, RSRP, MCS</p> <p><u>Aggregated</u>: Bits/Joules.</p>		<p>CHANNELS</p> <p>i2CAT's Board of trustees (industry, public sector, and academics)</p> <p>Spin-offs, venture builders</p> <p>Industrial/academic fairs</p>	<p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>Companies trying to adopt innovative solutions for O-RAN</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>TBD</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>TBD</p>		

5.2.2.2 IHP - Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics (IHP)

IHP will focus its exploitation on developing further the work on ISAC and integration of the developed solutions in different platforms internally available. IHP plans to exploit the results academically via its annual summer school, and lectures given at Universities in Berlin and the graduate school supporting PhD students at IHP. Resulting ISAC HW cores and SW implementations can be exploited together with the platforms via IHP's daughter company "IHP Solutions". The developed ISAC HW and SW cores will be offered to third parties for integration in their products. The acquired know-how can be used to help Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEMs) to develop their own products, supporting ISAC, in the form of consulting services. Additionally, IHP will file patents for the patentable algorithms and architectures for ISAC developed within this project.

During this project, many PhD students and interns will be involved in research and development of different ISAC aspects and algorithms as well as implementation approaches. This will contribute significantly towards their training in this field and will be a significant step towards producing engineers prepared for development of future products supporting ISAC.

Innovation:

The innovations for IHP focus on the research for introduction of the 6G ISAC into the RAN by leveraging radar type sensing into the typical 3GPP sensing of current 4G/5G RAN. These features are already part of the 3GPP Release-19 6G use-cases and will be features of 3GPP Release-20 6G Study Items and are also gaining industry and research momentum through initiatives such as the ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG) for ISAC. IHP is currently investigating paths for the potential exploitation of the work on ISAC in SNS Stream C/D projects for 2025 calls.

IHP demonstrated its Sub-6 ISAC system at the EuCNC 2025 conference in Poznan, Poland, and it is deeply looking into how RIS can complement and assist sensing in indoor scenarios.

5.2.2.3 Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC)

UPC is going to exploit its participation in BeGREEN project in order to further strengthen its ability to pursue research, development and teaching activities both for its own benefit and for the benefit of its country and the EU in general. In broad terms, the obtained expertise is expected to be applied to: (i) bring the forefront of technological development into their syllabuses to educate future engineers. (ii) Carry out doctoral and post-doctoral research in areas related to the project and, thanks to the cooperation between academia and industry during the project, foster the participation in programs such as Marie Skłodowska-Curie European Industrial Doctorate to help PhD candidates step outside academia. (iii) To improve the UPC's postgraduate and customized training courses, facilitating the convergence between research departments and public or private companies. (iv) To get aligned with the strategy for Horizon Europe 2021-2027 and stay competitive for future research initiatives in different domains (national programme, etc.).

At M12 of BeGREEN's project execution, some more detailed insight on exploitation plans can be provided, based on the work conducted in WP2, WP3 and WP4 as well as the dissemination actions already undertaken, which are associated to WP6.

From an academic perspective, there is undoubtable growing awareness and interest on sustainability and green communications. Students pursuing both the bachelor and master's degrees in Telecommunications at UPC (ETSETB-UPC) will have the chance from the academic year 2023/24 onwards to learn on such technical areas in several subjects: "5G Mobile Communications systems", "Artificial intelligence-enabled 5G networks" and "Wireless lab". The contents elaborated in these subjects leverage results and lesson learnt from BeGREEN. Furthermore, from the second term of the academic year 2023/24 onwards, a specific chapter discussing how the work in students' bachelor's and master's degrees thesis addresses sustainability

aspects will be compulsory included.

Innovation:

The main scientific problems addressed concerning the relay control and management mechanisms are:

- 1) Detection of coverage holes.
- 2) Fixed relay placement.
- 3) Candidate RUE identification.
- 4) Relay activation/deactivation process.

These problems are solved through the specification of the workflows reflecting the interactions between the components of the BeGREEN architecture and the development of algorithmic solutions that make use of AI-based models when appropriate.

Concerning other fronts of exploitation, UPC is considering two promising directions: (1) Building a Network Digital Twin (NDT) leveraging the simulation environment that is being built around UPC Campus as part of BeGREEN's activities in WP2, WP3 and WP4. Such NDT could be exploited in future SNS projects and/or in industrial collaborations (e.g., on-going collaboration with Telefonica), (2) Elaboration of selected algorithmic solutions developed in WP4 as xApps/rApps in order to progress towards their implementation and practical validation. Paths for possible further exploitation include open calls from SNS Stream C/D projects, future SNS projects in 2024 or 2025 calls as well as direct transfer to some other BeGREEN's partners or external companies.

5.2.3 SME partners

5.2.3.1 Accelleran (ACC)

ACC is an SME focusing on cloud-native O-RAN network functions (Near-RT RIC and CU) and RAN integration, especially targeted toward newer private and shared RAN (neutral host) 5G networks. The eco-system developed in BeGREEN and the resultant energy-saving capabilities will enable distinct competitive advantages (in OPEX savings from energy reduction) for ACC products and solutions and hence increased SOM. This will drive both shorter-term 5G-Advanced sales (e.g., the efficient ARM and accelerated hardware, RIC xApp driven energy-saving) and longer-term 6G (with RIS, distributed MIMO) roadmap of products. Monitoring of shorter-term commercial opportunities will be a priority for an SME such as ACC. The BeGREEN results, through Total cost of Ownership (TCO) reductions, will unlock new verticals and applications for Open B5G/6G solutions, increasing TAM. Resultant BeGREEN competitive advantages will increase the SAM through improved TCO for these new verticals and as 'greener' alternatives for current verticals (like Industrial/Enterprise private networks, shared dense urban deployments, etc.).

ACC individual exploitation plan

ACC will use BeGREEN results to foster the growth on energy saving in future RAN developments. For that, ACC will work on CU / RIC HW acceleration.

ACC will develop xApps to achieve energy efficiency (RU on/off control from the Near-Real Time RIC).

The value proposition delivered by this item is analyzed by ACC and presented in the following VP & Lean Canvases.

PROBLEM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficient OpenRAN deployment complexity High CAPEX of network High OPEX of network 	SOLUTION Develop xApps / rApps on Near-Real Time / Non-Real Time RIC to add intelligence on RU power management and improve energy efficiency. CU / RIC HW acceleration for performance improvement and energy efficiency.	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION Energy efficient CU on ARM xApps providing energy efficient on Open-RAN.	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE Use of A1 / O1 interfaces for Intelligence Plane	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> private enterprises MNOs
	EXISTING ALTERNATIVES Alternative is less energy efficient			
COST STRUCTURE Future SW Improvement		REVENUE STREAMS licenses and royalties		

Some of the BeGREEN results, especially the energy saving xApps and Intelligence Plane roadamp, have been directly beneficial in being selected for a recent commercial deployment of Open RAN based MNO urban densification solution for Belgian based Citymesh [15], so there have already been clear exploitation benefits for ACC, with the BeGREEN ‘energy saving’ being a strong commercial differentiator.

Some of the other BeGREEN results, like the ‘Intelligence Plane’ are being further researched and developed in the scope of SNS 6G-SENSES, to allow those joint BeGREEN/6G-SENSES results to be brought to market in the 2-5 year timeframe.

5.2.3.2 Gigasys Solutions (GIGASYS)

GIGASYS is an SME on wireless consultancy and R&D program management in the area of ICT. GIGASYS will use selected BeGREEN results for strengthening its consulting competency and to deliver value to its clients

in the telecommunications industry across Europe. The exploitation of BeGREEN results by GIGASYS follows a three-step process: i) Identification of exploitable project results on a continuous basis by GIGASYS' key personnel; ii) Generation of White Papers and other information items based on the identified exploitable project results; iii) Value creation for clients through discussions, follow-up research and innovation as well as consulting on emerging networks, services, and applications related to the identified exploitable project results. GIGASYS will advise its telco clients and partners via bi- and multi-lateral exchanges, targeted workshops, and community-internal White Papers. Furthermore, GIGASYS will use BeGREEN results to advise its clients on opportunities and risks arising from BeGREEN results and the impact they may have.

5.2.3.3 RunEL (REL)

REL is an SME considered a center of excellence for OFDMA technology, REL develops the Sparq-2025 family of hardware (FPGA) accelerators for 5G O-RUs and O-DUs that reduces the 5G Network latency below 1 millisecond and enable UE position measurement accuracy of 1 cm level. REL also developed an E2E 5G network that is currently being deployed in a Sport Stadium in Israel. REL participated in four Horizon 2020 projects (IoRL, 5GENESIS, Affordable 5G and 6G Brains) and was awarded the Innovation Radar award from the EU. REL will enhance the performance of its RU and DU solutions with the BeGREEN research results in terms of power radiation, power efficiency and power consumption.

Innovation:

RunEL (REL) will develop technologies and modules that will drastically improve the power efficiency of the Radio Unit (RU) in Cellular Networks

Below development will be done by REL in BeGREEN

1. Develop an AI based Digital Predistortion (DPD) and Envelope Tracking (ET) algorithms
2. Develop an RU RF Power Amplifier Blanking module

AI based Digital Predistortion (DPD) and Envelope Tracking (ET) algorithms

The goal is to take advantage of new Artificial Intelligence techniques to improve the performance of DPD and ET modules in the RU RF power amplifiers.

DPD Solution Description

DPD provides an effective method to linearize RF PA operation and minimize its distortion. The method is based on incorporating a nonlinear function (the inverse function of the amplifier) between the input signal and the amplifier to produce a linear output.

The DPD must adapt to PA variations with time, temperature, PA model variations/imperfections and more. Since those variations are difficult to represent with a deterministic model, an AI based model was used to perform the PA linearization.

ET Solution Description

5G OFDMA signals need to be amplified before transmission over the air with linear amplifiers to avoid distortion of the signal. The average Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR) of the OFDMA signal requires a Power Amplifier (PA) backoff of 10 dB to ensure linear signal amplification. This backoff means that the average PA energy efficiency lies in the 25-35 % range. Envelope Tracking (ET) is a method in which the power supply voltage applied to the RF PA is continuously adjusted ensuring the PA is operating at current peak power efficiency and as a result the PA energy consumption is reduced to the average energy and its energy efficiency is multiplied.

TRL level

The TRL Levels of the AI based DPD solution and the ET solutions are TRL-3 (experimental proof of concept) and the proof-of-concept results are presented in BeGREEN WP3 deliverables

Commercialization Plans

The AI based DPD and ET solutions are still under evaluation by the product management department at RunEL whether it can be incorporated in RunEL O-RU commercial product. The main question is if the Power Saving achieved by the AI based DPD and ET modules can justify the price increase due to the additional modules incorporated to the RU. A preliminary evaluation result is that the AI based DPD and ET modules will be cost effective in high Power RU products (5 Watts and Higher) rather than Small Cell products like the current Sparq-2025-SRU RunEL RU.

Radio Unit RF Power Amplifier Blanking module

The goal is to reduce the RU PA power consumption in medium and low traffic periods turning off the PA when there is no data in the downlink stream

PA Blanking Module Description

PA blanking stops the PA energy consumption for symbols without active data allocations. This is done by disconnecting the DC bias to the RU PAs when there is no data allocated in the OFDMA symbols that needed to be transmitted in the downlink to the User Equipment (UEs) in the RU coverage area.

When resources of a layer downlink symbol have no allocated data, the related RF PA will be blanked (momentarily shut down) for the symbol duration.

To make the PA Blanking module more efficient it is required that the scheduler in the Distributed Unit (DU) will be configured in a way that it will allocate the data in the OFDMA symbols in the Frequency domain rather than the Time domain to maximize the number of symbols that can be blanked by the PA Blanking Module at any time.

TRL level

The TRL Level of the PA Blanking Module is TRL-4 (technology validated in the lab) and the initial lab test results is presented in BeGREEN D3.2.

Commercialization Plans

The PA Blanking solution was already demonstrated at the sustainability stand in the last EuCNC 2025 conference in Poznan in June 2025. The PA blanking module is currently being incorporated in the RunEL Sparq-2025-SRU RU commercial product and will be provided to any new customer that will purchase the Radio.

5.2.4 Summary of individual exploitation plan

Summary of BeGREEN partners’ exploitation plans can be found in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2 Summary of BeGREEN Partners' Individual Plans

Partner	Interest in the Exploitation	Routes for Exploitation	Target Audience	Yearly Plan
ACC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop xApps to achieve RU power on/Off from RIC and work on energy efficiency. ACC will work on CU/RIC HW acceleration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop API and improve A1 and O1 interfaces. CU HW Acceleration (XDP / Security) Develop energy saving xApps 	Accelleran dRAX™ Open Interface RAN Intelligence customer	1) 2026/2026 2) 2026
GIGASYS	Use the inspiration by BeGREEN innovations in	Broaden the consultancy area using achieved experience and	Consultancy clients	2025, 2026

	consulting services to clients.	knowledge from the project.		
IHP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of ISAC algorithms, approaches and architectures for integration in 6G networks • Using sensing information for optimizing radio network energy efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents in developed algorithms and licensing via daughter company “IHP Solutions” • Potential integration within other products • Training of engineers and PhD students in future sensing technologies 	Industry and academia	2025, 2026
TSA	Define future network architectures	Simulation of different network topologies in different environments	Telecom industry, industrial deployments, internal management	TBD
UPC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing sustainability & energy efficiency in syllabus at UPC • Development of rApps/xApps for Relay management • Building NDT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bachelor and Master degrees in Telecommunications Engineering at UPC • SNS JU 2024 & 2025 calls 	Academia, Telecom industry	2024, 2025
BT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy management rApps/xApps • Mathematical energy models for various network components. • System-level simulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of rApps/xApps for running on local small-cell testbed • Development of such models. • Programming these energy models in system-level simulations. • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BT wireless research staff • BT/EE network operations • BT wireless research staff • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2026 • 2026 • 2026
NEC	RIS integration into O-RAN	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Developing an architecture to integrate RIS into O-RAN 2) Identifying the corresponding metrics to optimize RIS configuration 	NEC’s Telecom Services Business Unit	TBD
i2CAT	Offer innovative RAN Intelligent Control for O-RAN. RIS integration into O-RAN	Develop RIC and AI Engine platform. Develop RIS Control. Develop rApps/xApps targeting energy efficiency.	i2CAT board of trustees (private, public, academic).	TBD
REL	Offer the Green RU product developed in BeGREEN to RunEL vertical markets customers	RunEL Global Marketing and Sales Channels, Digital Media (Website and LinkedIn) and Integration partners	Global Private 5G Network operators and System integrators	2025 and on
PW	Energy saving in L1 processing algorithms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use energy efficient ARM architecture for L1 processing vs. legacy architectures. • Utilize already existing 	Operators that will use: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PW Products which are 	Using ARM: 2025 Using GPU:

		<p>GPUs in the system for L1 processing (e.g. GPUs which are used for other purposes such as AI) or adding dedicated GPUs. Use these GPUs for wireless performance improvement and power consumption reduction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reducing number of required CPU cores and thus reducing the operator’s equipment footprint and capex 	<p>based on ARM architecture.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possibly in the future: PW Products which are based on offloading some of the L1 algorithms to GPU 	TBD
LMI	Energy efficiency and energy saving in future developments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> energy saving in future RAN developments. promote new energy efficiency features in B5G and 6G 	Network Management and RAN customers	TBD

5.3 Joint exploitation plan

Throughout the project lifetime, the distinctions between ‘single-vendor’ and ‘multi-vendor’ Open RAN solutions has become a significant differentiator in the eco-system, including in market penetration, due to the increasingly understood complications, costs and risks of system integration and support. While Multi-vendor RAN is projected to reach \$2-3 billion by 2029 [16], current multi-vendor RAN adoption and expectations remain limited. Indeed, market concentration -as measured by the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI)- is rising across several regions. The RAN market is now classified as “highly concentrated” (HHI > 2500) in five of the six global regions. This suggests that the supplier diversity element of the Open RAN vision is struggling to materialise, despite other aspects of Open RAN becoming mainstream.

This effect is also seen in the following BeGREEN partner joint exploitation plans, where the plans at the end of the project are significantly limited, compared to the enthusiasm and interest at the beginning and earlier phases of BeGREEN.

5.3.1 Partners joint exploitation plan

Exploitation activities: addressing the exploitation of the project results by the various partners of the consortium, with a particular focus on joint exploitation.

Opportunities for joint exploitation of project results were analyzed throughout the project, as part of the work in T6.4. However, the final result of joint exploitation is limited.

5.3.1.1 Joint exploitation CU HW Acceleration (ACC-ARM)

CU HW acceleration was an opportunity for ACC and ARM to focus on energy efficiency and produce a valuable joint product line for different market. ACC and ARM are planning to incorporate an energy efficient server which most efficiently fits CU with (XDP / Security) different traffic scenarios. According to ACC-ARM joint exploitation plan, energy efficient CU will be tested in BeGREEN project timeframe, and first time was disseminated during the EuCNC conference in June 2024.

However, as described in 5.2.1.4, with ARM discontinuing activities in in BeGREEN, due to their strategic shift

away from the RAN chipset market provision, no true joint ACC-ARM exploitation plans now exist.

With the benefits of BeGREEN porting and testing on ARM platforms, ACC still foresees the possibility to deliver Open RAN solutions based on ARM architectures (e.g. SoC chipsets with ARM CPUs), based on commercial market demand and performance/cost benefits but current CPU platforms are x86 based.

5.3.1.2 Joint exploitation DU HW Acceleration (PW-ARM)

PW are planning to offer MNOs cloud based L1 solutions which are implemented over ARM architectures in their future projects and products. This will help improving N/W energy efficient compared to legacy x86 solutions. The solutions will include the modules being developed within BeGREEN but also other parts of the L1 transceiver.

5.3.1.3 Joint exploitation RIS integration into O-RAN (I2CAT-NEC)

I2CAT and NEC will join efforts to develop the necessary interfaces for seamless integration of RIS within the O-RAN architecture. This collaboration focuses on innovation and interoperability, as both entities recognize the transformative potential of jointly exploiting RIS integration. By pooling their expertise and resources, I2CAT and NEC aim to define interfaces and protocols that will facilitate the seamless deployment and management of RIS elements within the O-RAN framework. This collaborative endeavour not only accelerates the adoption of RIS technology but also sets a precedent for future collaborations in EU projects.

5.3.1.4 Joint exploitation multi-vendor O-RAN (ACC-REL)

Since ACC makes the RIC and CU network functions in the dRAX product line and REL makes RUs, joint exploitation of ACC and REL products requires a 3rd party DU solution.

ACC supports srsRAN based DU (with F1 HLS split towards ACC CU and E2 interfacing towards ACC Near-RT RIC) but due to time/effort constraints and commercial priorities REL implemented their BeGREEN innovations in their own CU/DU stack, using scheduler-driven blanking in their proprietary DU MAC scheduler (TRL 3-4), but this is not currently O-RAN fronthaul compatible and could not be integrated into a system-wide PoC, thereby needing further R&I maturity towards TRL-6.

There are no current obvious ACC-REL joint exploitation plans, though further collaboration in R&I project to target this is still actively considered.

5.3.1.5 Joint exploitation O-RAN Intelligence plane (ACC-I2CAT)

The Intelligence Plane developed in BeGREEN provides a novel framework for developing AI-driven rApps/xApps and integrate them with O-RAN RICs. This was an opportunity for Accelleran to enhance its dRAX product and for i2CAT in order to explore new license transfer agreements.

ACC and i2CAT have a long track record of collaboration in previous 5G-PPP projects, which led to the integration of i2CAT RICs with Accelleran's dRAX product. Additionally, i2CAT's spin-off, Neutron, which is commercializing management systems for private 5G networks, may facilitate the joint exploitation of this asset. ACC customers interested in enhancing dRAX framework with AI-driven rApps/xApps to optimize its network management operations would be targeted audience. Also, rApp/xApp or ML model developers (e.g., ACC or i2CAT themselves) could exploit this asset to develop novel solutions which could be applied to ACC's product or transferred to other O-RAN RIC vendors.

The joint exploitation of the BeGREEN Intelligence Plane (PoC#1) is limited in scope AI/ML in the SMO (Non-RT RIC with rApps) and Near-RT RIC (with xApps). The integration of this IPR and functionality is now being considered by ACC product management to further mature the offering before commercial exploitation in 2025-2026 timeframe, subject to any IPR negotiations.

5.3.1.6 Joint exploitation O-RAN Intelligence plane for ISAC (ACC-IHP)

Due to the PoC#1 success, combined with the excellent PoC#2 sensing research (as demonstrated @ EuCNC 2024 & 2025), there was a joint research & later exploitation potential identified in leveraging the BeGREEN PoC#1 AI/ML and PoC#2 into integrated AI/ML for 6G ISAC.

This is being further jointly research in 6G-SENSES by IHP & ACC.

While BeGREEN focussed on AI/ML in the SMO (Non-RT RIC) and Near-RT RIC, 6G-SENSES is researching the deeper ISAC functionality into the DU, researching both embedded of ISAC AI/ML processing in the DU via dApps & extension of the exporting of the ISAC telemetry through extensions of the O-RAN E2 interface with a ISAC E2SM towards the Near-RT RIC and it’s xApps.

With the 6G-SENSES research in the 2024-2026 timeframe, anticipated to TRL 5, the joint commercial exploitation towards TRL 7 is expected in the 2027-2028 timeframe, with goal of driving and aligning with 6G ISAC standardisation. This is considered indirect BeGREEN joint exploitation.

5.3.2 Summary of joint exploitation plans

Partner	Interest in the Exploitation	Routes for Exploitation	Target Customer	Yearly Plan
ACC, ARM	ACC will work on CU/RIC HW acceleration.	ACC selling Private 5G solutions running on ARM platforms	Industrial Private 5G Stand-Alone Non-Public Network (SNPN) verticals	2025-2027
PW, ARM	Energy saving in L1 processing algorithms.	Use energy efficient ARM architecture for L1 processing	Operators that will use PW Products which are based on ARM architecture.	2025-2027
I2CAT, NEC	RIS integration into O-RAN	Integration of RIS in O-RAN	Telecom Services Business Unit	2025-2026
ACC, REL	Multi-vendor O-RAN	Further potential R&I projects	TBD	TBD
ACC, I2CAT	Provide an Intelligence Plane for enabling AI-driven optimisations in O-RAN	Mature from TRL 3-4 has been pushed towards TRL6 in R&I before commercialisation. The scope can be broadened including sensing and reach higher TRLs	Industrial Private 5G (SNPN) verticals	2025-2026
ACC, IHP	O-RAN Intelligence plane for 6G ISAC	Through 6G-SENSES research in 2024-2026 timeframe, anticipated to TRL 5-6, joint commercial exploitation towards TRL 7 expected in 2027-2028	Industrial Private 5G (SNPN) verticals, especially critical infrastructure & dual-use	2027-2028

6 Updated Projections for BeGREEN Relevant Market Sizing

The BeGREEN proposal contained market estimations for the potential commercial exploitation of the developed technologies and resultant products, based on O-RAN Alliance or Open RAN standards.

This market has evolved since the writing of that proposal and an update was provided in deliverable D6.2 (with final submission 28/10/2024).

This chapter presents the updated market estimates both for Open RAN solutions in general and more specifically ones leveraging the OPEX savings through BeGREEN energy savings and the market share addressed by products that are differentiated by energy efficiency and sustainability criteria.

6.1 Target Markets Addressed by BeGREEN Open RAN Solutions

The large RAN vendors (such as Ericsson, Nokia, Huawei), while initially hostile or at least ambivalent to Open RAN, seeing it as a threat to their market share, have increasingly started to adopt these technologies in their products (or at least their marketing).

This, together with real issues of multi-vendor product interoperability and complications of 'RAN integration', has seen the emergence of the 'Single Open RAN vendors' terminology, targeted towards traditional Public MNOs (or Telcos) customers as well as for Private 5G deployments based on both single and multi-vendor solutions.

There has also seen a big rise of newer Asian vendors (especially NEC of Japan and Samsung of Korea) leveraging this to enhance their market share in these traditional MNO markets.

However, for new and smaller vendors, the primary market for Open RAN products and solutions is for the emerging 'Private 5G' (or NPN: Non-Public Networks) for new vertical applications such as manufacturing, industrial, mining and other B2B (Business to Business) types of markets, with services provisioned either 'do it yourself' SNPN, through newer CSP (Communication Service Providers) or SI (System Integrators) or through established MNO looking to expand from purely consumer B2C to also B2B service offerings (typically with higher margins).

These 'Private 5G' networks have initially been truly private (SNPN) for initial 'richer' verticals, where cost is not a major consideration, but it is increasingly evolving towards Shared Private 5G (using neutral host RAN sharing or sharing of Public networks PNI-NPN), where the affordability imperative constrains the business plans.

This distinction between 'single-vendor' and 'multi-vendor' Open RAN solutions has become significant in market penetration, due to the increasingly understood complications, costs and risks of system integration and support.

6.2 General Open RAN Solution Market Sizing

The market for private and shared RAN networks based on Open RAN technologies was expected to grow rapidly. In 2024, the Open RAN market was valued at approximately **USD 2.8 billion**. Projections indicate this market will expand at a **compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 39.4%**, reaching **USD 20.9 billion by 2030** [17] [18].

This growth is driven by factors such as increased **adoption of 5G networks**, the demand for greater **network flexibility**, and **multi-vendor ecosystems** that reduce the cost of deploying and operating mobile networks [18]. Open RAN solutions align well with cloud-native architectures, further accelerating adoption in both **private networks and hybrid cloud deployments** [19].

By **2033**, the Open RAN market could grow to **USD 32 billion**, supported by ongoing regulatory efforts and

collaborative industry initiatives to promote open standards and vendor diversification [20] [21]. The rising popularity of **greenfield deployments**, which allow providers to build new infrastructure using best-in-class technology, is also fueling market growth. These deployments emphasize **vendor flexibility** and encourage innovation in building future-oriented networks [17, 19].

However, in the latest market reports, worldwide RAN revenues, excluding services, are projected to stay flat and reach \$160 B in cumulative revenue over the 2025-2029 forecast period [22]. The RAN segments that are expected to grow over the next five years include 5G NR, Open RAN and Private 5G.

In 2022, the global market for RAN products generated about \$45 billion in revenues, according to Omdia. Two years later, the figure had plummeted to \$35 billion. 5G had not brought revenue gains for telcos, and data traffic growth was slowing. Operators responded by slashing expenditure. This was bad news for kit vendors, prompting mass layoffs as revenues fell. At Ericsson's mobile networks unit, sales dropped 6% on a constant-currency basis last year, while Nokia's equivalent business group suffered a 21% decline in revenues.

However, Open RAN markets are stabilizing with year-over-year revenue growth in 2025 and with long-term Open RAN growth prospects remaining favourable [16].

6.3 Projected Market Sizing of BeGREEN enabled OPEX savings through Energy Efficiency

The primary benefits of the BeGREEN innovations is reduction of energy consumption, leading to Open RAN OPEX reduction, hence TCO.

In mobile networks based on 3GPP standards, **15-40%** of the **OPEX** is attributed to energy costs, primarily due to the power consumption of RAN elements, such as base stations. This percentage varies depending on the network architecture, technology generation (e.g., 4G, 5G), and the deployment environment. RAN is the largest consumer of energy within the network, accounting for up to **60-70% of the total energy consumption** in many cases [23] [24] [25] [26].

Operators are adopting energy-saving technologies, such as AI-driven traffic optimization and sleep-mode functions, to reduce energy expenditures. The increasing deployment of Open RAN technologies also provides new opportunities to enhance energy efficiency by enabling more flexible and dynamic network management through multi-vendor environments [25] [26].

Quantifying the impact of adopting **advanced O-RAN-based energy savings** on the **Total Addressable Market (TAM)**, **Serviceable Available Market (SAM)**, and **Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM)** requires assessing the extended market potential created through energy efficiency, reduced operating costs, and increased scalability. Below is an analysis of the projected market increases:

6.3.1 TAM Increase

The **TAM** represents the total market potential for O-RAN-based solutions. With traditional 3GPP networks expected to expand but facing cost limitations due to energy demands, introducing advanced energy-saving solutions—such as ML-based traffic steering and dynamic load management—creates additional TAM.

1. **Impact:** The Open RAN market is projected to grow from **USD 2.8 billion in 2024 to USD 20.9 billion by 2030**, at a **CAGR of 39.4%** [17] [18].
2. **Quantification:** Energy-efficient features are likely to increase TAM by an additional **10-15%** beyond baseline growth, as these solutions attract enterprises focused on green technology, smart cities, and 5G industrial use cases [27] [28].

6.3.2 SAM Increase

The **SAM** reflects the portion of the TAM that is realistically serviceable based on infrastructure and deployment feasibility. With energy-saving strategies, operators can unlock more cost-effective deployments and address regions and use cases previously unviable due to high energy costs.

1. **Impact:** By adopting **O-RAN energy-efficient strategies**, the SAM could increase by **15-20%** as operators can tap into new energy-conscious sectors, such as **private 5G networks, smart manufacturing, and critical infrastructure** [29] [28]. Reduced operational costs also allow operators to deploy networks in remote and underserved areas, further expanding the SAM.

6.3.3 SOM Increase

The **SOM**, or market share, reflects the actual portion of the SAM that operators can capture. Advanced O-RAN energy savings improve network efficiency and competitiveness, which translates into higher market penetration.

1. **Impact:** According to industry reports, operators adopting advanced O-RAN energy-saving technologies may achieve **10-20% higher market share** than those relying solely on traditional 3GPP solutions [27] [28].
2. **Quantification:** The improved cost structure and energy efficiency provide a competitive advantage in both consumer and enterprise segments, likely resulting in a **5-10% incremental market share gain** across key 5G services [28].

6.3.4 Summary

Incorporating **advanced BeGREEN O-RAN-based energy savings** can drive:

1. **TAM Increase:** 10-15% additional growth by expanding into new sectors and use cases.
2. **SAM Increase:** 15-20% expansion by reducing deployment costs and enabling access to previously unserved markets.
3. **SOM Increase:** 10-20% higher market share due to competitive advantages and enhanced cost efficiency.

7 KPI/KVI Assessment

Since the work carried out in BeGREEN’s WP2, many activities have taken place in the context of the SNS JU framework, fostered by the SNS community and the projects therein. A concrete and representative example of work in this topic is the SNS JU White Paper on “6G KVIS – SNS PROJECTS INITIAL SURVEY RESULTS 2025” [30].

From the organization of the chapter perspective, and as recalled in deliverable D2.2 [8], a structured KVI framework tailored to the ICT research and development (R&D) sector was proposed in [7]. This framework builds upon the familiar engineering approach of using KPIs to find a process that systematically integrates considerations of economic, social and ecological impact into technological development projects.

As a recap to the work initiated in deliverable D2.1 [7], we include in Table 7-1 the initial use cases considered in the project.

Table 7-1 BeGREEN Use Cases Defined in BeGREEN D2.1 [7]

Physical layer reference use cases
PHY#1 - B5G energy efficiency enhanced RAN through relay nodes
PHY#2 - Densification of the radio access architecture
PHY#3 - General mMIMO incentives
PHY#4 - Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS)
System-level reference use cases
SYS#1 - Energy efficiency in vRAN deployments with shared computing infrastructure
SYS#2 - Joint Orchestration of vRAN and Mobile Edge AI Services
SYS#3 - Traffic-aware management of NFV user-plane functions
SYS#4 - RIC driven energy-efficient RU on/off control

The project provided both the link from project-specific use cases to 6G use cases, and defined the expected Key Values (KVs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs) to take into consideration in BeGREEN. These are captured in Table 7-2.

Table 7-2 KVIs for the UCs Addressed by BeGREEN

6G UC	BeGREEN UC (as of D2.1 [7])	KV as Criterion and Goal	KV as Outcome	UC KVIs
#1 Ubiquitous access	PHY#1, PHY#2, PHY#3, PHY#4	Environmental Sustainability Digital Inclusion	KV1: Services are accessible and available to everyone KV2: Network capabilities are environmentally responsible, energy efficient Stakeholder: Experimenters, Researchers, MNOs, Verticals	Service Availability
#2 Digital Twin	PHY#4	Societal Sustainability, Environmental Sustainability	KV1: Improvements to customer experience KV2: Ability to test changes before they are implemented Stakeholder: Customers, Experimenters, Researchers	Network optimisation
#3 Physical and Environment Awareness	PHY#2, PHY#3, PHY#4, SYS#4	Economical Sustainability and innovation, Environmental Sustainability	KV1: Energy efficiency optimization KV2: Network capabilities are environmentally responsible, energy efficient Stakeholder: MNOs, Verticals	Energy efficiency
#4 Towards	SYS#1, SYS#2,	Economical	KV1: Cost-efficient networks	Cost,

Disaggregated and Virtualized Networks	SYS#3	Sustainability and innovation, Digital Inclusion, Environmental Sustainability	KV2: Energy efficiency optimization Stakeholder: MNOs	Resource utilization
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We provide next a brief analysis of the conclusions from the project regarding the KVIs defined in the project (last column of Table 7-2).

- **Service Availability KVI (6G use case #1)**

The topics tackled in the project, such as the evaluation of Cell-Free architectures, provide an insight of how this novel architecture can serve the same users as in C-MIMO reducing the transmit power by up to 30 dB without degrading performance. Increased functional performance is achieved and offers the flexibility to activate a reduced number of APs, i.e. number of RF chains.

Another topic heavily researched in the project is the use of relays in 6G. While the relay nodes have been traditionally considered as a tool to enhance the coverage conditions, BeGREEN has also proven that they can also contribute to reducing the energy consumption in the network [31].

- **Network Optimisation KVI (6G use case #2)**

The new capabilities that BeGREEN addresses, such as sensing, relays and the use of RIS panels do provide the means and flexibility to the RAN to perceive the environment (sensing), allow for flexibility regarding the placement of the elements (relays and RIS) providing valuable data to an O-RAN system for network optimisation. Extensive studies, e.g. simulations, have been provided on these new capabilities that allow for testing in advance performance measures and the identification of potential energy savings before a real deployment is rolled out.

- **Energy Efficiency KVI (6G use case #3)**

Studies made in the context of the project related to the shift to cell-free architectures do provide insights on how much energy efficiency can be gained. Physical and environmental awareness made possible by sensing implementations (such as the Sub-6 sensing system) provide means to reduce energy efficiency by directing the communication to the users and not wasting energy in pointing to undesired directions and, in addition, the fact of turning off some of the BSs and turning on the optimal BS based on the scenario (based on the sensing data), the power consumption can be reduced up to 50%.

- **Cost Resource utilization KVI (6G use case #4)**

An energy-aware implementation of AI services at the network edge is increasingly important for performance, economic and environmental reasons. In deliverable D4.3 [32] we have used a Bayesian learning algorithm to automated the identification of a policy that minimises the aggregate energy costs while adhering to predetermined performance criteria. Remarkably, this framework comes with minimal assumptions and is proved particularly effective in exploring the huge system configuration space. The proposed resource control mechanism is fully compliant with O-RAN and particularly promising for enabling edge AI services, as we verify experimentally using a prototype.

8 Standardisation

This section summarises the additional standardization activities carried out in the context of the project:

Change Request Description – CR R1-2310562

This Change Request (CR R1-2310562) proposes an update to the 3GPP Technical Specification TS 37.213, specifically concerning the Energy Detection (ED) Threshold formula used in shared spectrum channel access procedures for Rel-17. The modification aligns the 3GPP specification with the most recent updates introduced in ETSI EN 301 893 V2.1.52. This specification sets out the regulatory framework for RLAN operations in the 5 GHz and 6 GHz bands, including the definition of the Energy Detection Threshold Level (ED-TL). According to this standard, equipment must consider a channel as occupied when RLAN transmissions are detected above the ED TL, which is calculated across the total Nominal Channel Bandwidth of all Operating Channels used by the device.

Following the release of ETSI EN 301 893 V2.1.52 on September 22, 2023, key modifications were introduced, including revised power limits and an adjusted ED Threshold Level. Given that the original specification in TS 37.213 referenced the earlier ETSI EN 301 893 V2.1.1, this CR ensures continued regulatory compliance by updating the related text and formulae to reflect the new ED TL definition.

The proposal was introduced during 3GPP TSG-RAN WG1 Meeting #114bis, held in Xiamen, China, from October 9–13, 2023. The full CR document can be accessed via the following link: https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/TSG_RAN/WG1_RL1/TSGR1_114b/Docs/R1-2310562.zip

This update is essential for ensuring that 3GPP specifications remain aligned with current European regulatory requirements, thereby supporting compliant deployment of shared spectrum access technologies.

9 Summary and Conclusions

This document reported the dissemination and communication, liaison and exploitation activities that took place during the last months of the project.

The outcomes of this deliverable are the following:

- Many dissemination activities have taken place throughout the duration of the project, with important scientific publications accepted in highly ranked conferences and journals and plenty of interventions in Workshops, Special Sessions and Panels at 5G/6G events.
- An important presence from BeGREEN contributors to SNS and 6G IA frameworks, from the leadership of White Papers, preparation of Workshops to pure technical contributions in many of the activities promoted within the frameworks.
- Updated exploitation plans and market outlooks are given, relevant to the Open RAN and specifically BeGREEN innovation commercial exploitation potential.

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